

The BIM and BEM integration – opportunities, limitations, and influence on building design

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Abstract

The interest of the AEC industry in building energy modelling is not new. BEM is a powerful tool to assess and control the building's energy performance. It assists both AEC professionals and building owners in reaching their sustainability goals and limits energy consumption and the project's cost. BEM can be integrated at different design stages, from the concept design to construction and management. This work is interested in the BIM-BEM integration at the early design stage. The main focus of the proposed thesis is to investigate the state-of-the-art in the field of BIM and BEM integration. In particular, to highlight opportunities and limitations of integrating the energy performance evaluation of buildings with BIM models from the point of view of the building designer. Of particular interest is the identification of (i) benefits vs drawbacks, (ii) impacts on the workflow, and (iii) potential for increasing the final design's performance. The literature review revealed the lack of research about process maps favouring technical aspects and the need to improve BEM-related standards. The results of the practical case demonstrated that a software-specific process map is needed to ensure a seamless BIM-BEM integration workflow. The respect of a clear and comprehensive process map adapted to an early design stage increases the efficiency of the workflow, coordination, and productivity. It also assists the designer with exploring more design options in a relatively short time, improving the design in respect of sustainability goals.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/QSWX6daR6Mw>

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